

Development and evaluation of learning resources

**Creating an examples collection for the
“Be Smart About Your Health” resources:
part of the CHOICE project**

Jenny Moberg

Working paper, January 09, 2023

besmarthealth.org

www.informedhealthchoices.org

Colophon

<i>Title</i>	Creating an examples collection for the “Be Smart About Your Health” resources: part of the CHOICE project
<i>Authors</i>	Jenny Moberg jmoberg@doctors.org.uk
<i>Citation</i>	Moberg J. Creating an examples collection for the “Be Smart About Your Health” resources: part of the CHOICE project. IHC Working paper, 2023. Norwegian Institute of Public Health.
<i>Article category</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> About Informed Health Choices <input type="checkbox"/> Key concepts and glossary <input type="checkbox"/> Learning resources <input type="checkbox"/> Systematic reviews <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Development and evaluation of learning resources <input type="checkbox"/> Contextualising learning resources <input type="checkbox"/> <input type="checkbox"/> Claim evaluation tools <input type="checkbox"/> Editorials and commentaries <input type="checkbox"/> Grant applications
<i>Date</i>	January 2023

Figure 1: Searchable examples collection

Figure 2: Details of an example entry

Supplementary file: Results from conversations with students about conditions and interventions

Background

In the CHOICE research project^{1 2}, we sought to develop and evaluate educational resources for secondary schools to teach critical thinking about health information and choices, based on the Informed Health Choices Key Concepts³. The use of examples to illustrate concepts is an effective teaching strategy for teaching critical thinking.⁴ Therefore, finding good examples became an important part of developing the resources. Feedback from CHOICE project stakeholders and participants (students, teachers, and curriculum developers in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda) indicated that:

- Examples were helpful for teachers to try and clarify things when there were misunderstandings.
- Examples work best when they are understandable, interesting, and relatable for students.
- There should be examples to illustrate all the key concepts, and different types of interventions (health actions) - lifestyle changes, public health actions, medications, and other interventions.
- There should be examples to illustrate reliable and unreliable claims, reliable and unreliable research, effective and non-effective interventions, and lack of evidence.
- Generic treatment names, possibly with local names added in brackets, should be used to avoid different brand names in different countries.
- It was sensible to include Covid 19-related examples because the development and evaluation of the *Be Smart* resources happened during the pandemic and claims about health actions to prevent and cure Covid-19 were everywhere.
- It may be helpful to ask students to generate their own examples. However, teaching with unfamiliar examples requires an understanding of the key concepts and the example, and some teachers may not feel confident to do this.

We needed to collect a broad range of examples to illustrate the Key Concepts in the lessons and teacher training materials, both for students and teachers. At the same time, we recognised that many examples of interventions (health actions) could potentially be used to illustrate more than one concept.

Objective

To create a searchable collection of health actions that can be used as examples to illustrate Key Concepts in the *Be Smart About Your Health (Be Smart)*

resources, for secondary school students (aged 14 to 16), including brief plain language summaries of the evidence for each example.

Methods

We started by creating a list of conditions and health actions that are relevant and interesting to teenagers in East Africa. At the start of the project, we interviewed and conducted focus groups with students in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda to identify conditions and health actions. We used these and other examples in prototypes of the *Be Smart* resources.

We expanded on these examples by searching in publications for conditions and health actions that are relevant to teenagers,^{5 6} websites that provide evidence-based information about conditions and health actions that are commonly searched for,^{7 8 9} and websites that are about teen health globally and in Africa.^{10 11 12}

Our research teams in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda discussed suitable examples and consulted their national curriculum boards to identify any examples that should **not** be used in the *Be Smart* resources.

Through the project's student networks in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda, we identified two teenagers in each country who were willing to participate in online conversations exploring which topics they consider relevant and interesting. We explained this to the students' parents and obtained their consent. We provided the students with data packages to cover the cost of their online participation. Using WhatsApp, we conducted several semi-structured conversations country by country. For the potential examples we had collected, we explored whether the students had heard of the conditions and health actions, what they called them, where they would go to get help or what they would do, what health actions they thought work for the conditions, and what else they knew or had seen or heard about the conditions and health actions.

We asked each student to rate their interest in each health action and condition on a score from one to five, taking into consideration how important they thought it was to them and to other people their age. We calculated a mean score for each condition and health action.

Results

We created a set of examples for use in the *Be Smart* lessons. Based on the information from the conversations with students, we changed some of the examples we had initially included and added additional examples, using conditions and health actions that had a mean interest score over three (see **Supplementary file**).

Figure 1: Searchable examples collection

Heath actions	Health problem or goal	Show details
applying cow dung	burns	Show Details
applying creams for pain, gels for pain, ointments for pain	ankle sprain, muscle pain, joint pain	Show Details
applying mashed avocado	acne (spots, pimples)	Show Details
applying sugar paste	burns	Show Details
applying toothpaste	acne (spots, pimples)	Show Details
blood letting	infections, many conditions	Show Details
breathing in steam	Covid-19, flu, common cold	Show Details

Figure 2: Details of an example entry

applying toothpaste **acne (spots, pimples)** [Hide Details](#)

Claimed effects makes pimples (spots) go away

Actual effects There is no evidence that toothpaste is a good treatment for pimples (spots/acne), and it can cause irritation to skin.

Evidence summary A hint found on many websites is that toothpaste can dry up individual spots. While toothpaste does have antibacterial substances, it also contains substances that can irritate and damage your skin so it may not be preferable.

References: Kameswararao K, Sujani C, Koteswararao NV, Rajarao A, Satyanarayanamma PN. A Brief Review on Acne Vulgaris. *Research journal of Pharmacology and Pharmacodynamics*. 2019 Jul 1;11(3):109–19, and How the Internet is Changing us, our Patients and our Practice. *Indian Dermatology Online Journal*. 2021 Jul;12(4):593.

We developed the collection by creating a Google spreadsheet of all 74 health actions used as examples in the final version of the *Be Smart* resources. The spreadsheet includes: a) which lessons each health action is used as an example, b) the condition or reason for the health action, c) the claimed and actual effects of the health action, c) which key concepts the health action illustrates or could be used to illustrate, and d) the evidence.

To determine the evidence for examples, we searched for systematic reviews of the effects of each health action, and other evidence when we could not find a systematic review. For each health action, we listed the “actual effects” based on the evidence we found, we summarised key messages based on the evidence, and we included the reference for the evidence.

The Google spreadsheet is the back end for a searchable collection of health actions that is included as an Extra resource in the *Be Smart* resources (see *Figure 1 and 2*). The collection can be sorted and browsed based on the health actions or the condition (health problem or goal). Examples can be selected for each lesson in which they are used or could be used, and by each key concept that they are used to illustrate or could be used to illustrate, and the collection can be searched.

Teachers can use this resource to find research evidence about the examples already used in the lessons and to find new examples that could be used in the lessons. The resource includes templates to help teachers use the information in the collection to create claims or choices that can be used to illustrate the key concepts. Instructions on how to search and use the collection are included in the Teachers’ guide section of the *Be Smart* resources.

Limitations

There were some practical difficulties with conducting the exploratory conversations with the young people in Kenya, Rwanda, and Uganda. Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, it was not possible to do face-to-face interviews. We, therefore, used Whatsapp, for which the participants mainly used their parents’ smartphones on Sundays. The reception was often bad and although video calls had been planned, the conversations often ended up being by text in real time. This worked quite well but probably resulted in less rich detail and explains why we did not obtain interest scores from all six teenagers for all of the examples.

Sexual health is an important topic for teenagers,¹³ and related topics scored highly in terms of interest to the teenagers. Due to concern that curriculum committees may prefer for the resources for our target age group not to contain sexual health examples, we decided to include anti-retroviral treatment for HIV as an example, but no other sexual health examples. This means a highly relevant and interesting set of examples is largely missing from the collection of examples.

Conclusion

Examples for use in the Be Smart About Your Health resources are free to access: <https://besmarthealth.org/health-actions>. The collection is not exhaustive but provides many examples that are relevant for East African teenagers and that they are likely to find interesting.

- 1 <https://prosjektbanken.forskingsradet.no/project/FORISS/284683?Kilde=FORISS&distribution=Ar&chart=bar&calcType=funding&Sprak=no&sortBy=date&sortOrder=desc&resultCount=30&offset=0&Prosjektleder=Andrew+David+Oxman>
- 2 <https://www.informedhealthchoices.org/secondary-school-resources/>
- 3 <https://zenodo.org/record/6611932#.ZAITIezMLYI>
- 4 Philip C. Abrami PC, Bernard RM, Borokhovski E, Waddington DI, Wade CA and Persson T. Strategies for Teaching Students to Think Critically: A Meta-Analysis Review of Educational Research. Published online 25 September 2014. DOI: 10.3102/0034654314551063
- 5 Werner David et al. *Where There Is No Doctor : A Village Health Care Handbook*. Rev ed Rev ed. Hesperian Health Guides 2013.
- 6 Bukenya, J.N., Canavan, C.R., Bärnighausen, T. and Fawzi, W.W. (2020), Strengthening our knowledge base and research capacity for improved adolescent health in sub-Saharan Africa: a South–South–North collaboration. *Trop Med Int Health*, 25: 2-4.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/tmi.13342>
- 7 <https://thatsaclaim.org/health/>
- 8 <https://www.evidentlycochrane.net/making-health-decisions-things-that-can-help/>
- 9 <https://www.informedhealth.org/topic-areas/>
- 10 <https://www.afro.who.int/health-topics/adolescent-health#:~:text=Most%20young%20people%20are%20thought%20of%20as%20healthy.part%20of%20the%20Child%20and%20Adolescent%20Health%20Programme.>
- 11 <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/adolescents-health-risks-and-solutions>
- 12 <https://www.healthforteens.co.uk/>

-
- 13 Bukenya, J.N., Canavan, C.R., Bärnighausen, T. and Fawzi, W.W. (2020),
Strengthening our knowledge base and research capacity for improved
adolescent health in sub-Saharan Africa: a South-South-North
collaboration. *Trop Med Int Health*, 25: 2-4.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/tmi.13342>